

Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), and adaptive trials and in crop cutting experiments in farmers' fields.

Yield increase was 14-40% compared with IR20 and 13-15% compared with Jaya (see table). In AICRIP trials, it was superior to Jaya at six locations during the wet season and two locations during the dry season.

ADT39 is resistant to bacterial blight, blast, neck blast, brown spot, sheath blight, and grain discoloration;

moderately resistant to green leafhopper; and susceptible to sheath rot, leafhopper, and brown planthopper. (However, BPH is not a problem in the season in which it is grown.)

ADT39 has 65% milling recovery and 10.1% protein. The fine-grained rice cooks well and is highly preferred in South India. Farmers of Tamil Nadu have named it "Idly rice" and "tiffin rice." The Agricultural Department

estimated its natural spread, before release, in 40,000 ha in Thanjavur district.

ADT39 is already proven well suited to late planting (Oct-Nov) in Thanjavur district. Because it matures earlier than IR20, it should escape water scarcity during ripening, opening room for timely sowing of black gram, green gram, and cotton in the rice fallow season. □

VL Dhan 163 - a new upland rice variety for Uttar Pradesh hills

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VL Dhan 163, a derivative of IR5904, was released in 1987 for upland Jun sowing in the U.P. hills.

VL Dhan 163 possesses such desirable characteristics as semitall stature, medium grain, and compact panicle with good spikelet fertility. It has moderate tillering ability and matures in 108-113 d. It is tolerant of drought and

low temperature and shows good response up to 60 kg N/ha. It also has shown high resistance to leaf and neck blast, stem borer, and leafhopper (see table).

In 12 trials at different sites in the U.P. hills, VL Dhan 163 produced an average 2.6 t/ha, 41.35% higher than the

national check Bala.

Traditionally, the hill farmers of U.P. grow Mar- or Apr-sown spring rice under rainfed upland conditions in a 2-yr cropping system of spring rice - wheat - finger millet - fallow. With VL Dhan 163, hill farmers will be able to plant two rice crops in a year. □

Plant characteristics of VL Dhan 163 and Bala. Almora, U. P., India, 1987.

Character	VL Dhan 163	Bala (check)
Plant height (cm)	95-100	65-70
Days to 50% flowering	75-80	80-85
Days to maturity	108-113	105-110
1000-grain weight (g)	19.0	16.0
Hulling percentage	85.4	83.7
Grain length (mm)	5.4	4.6
Grain width (mm)	2.2	2.4
Length/width ratio	2.4	1.9
Protein content	9.3	9.0
Yield (t/ha)	2.6	1.8
<i>Disease & insect pest reaction^a</i>		
Leaf blast (0-9 scale)	3	9
Neck blast (0-9 scale)	1	9
Sheath rot (0-9 scale)	3	7
False smut (0-9 scale)	1	5
Stem borer (0-9 scale)	3	5
Leafhopper (0-9 scale)	1	5

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice. Maximum score recorded during any year 1983-86.

Performance of semidwarf mutants of Basmati 370

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Four semidwarf mutants (gamma

radiation 25 kR) were selected from the segregating population and yield tested in the field. The short-statured mutants gave significantly higher grain yields than parent variety Basmati 370 and had high tillering ability (Table 1) and lodging resistance. Growth duration was similar to Basmati 370. The semidwarf

Table 1. Performance of the induced mutant lines and Basmati 370. Punjab, Pakistan.

Mutant, variety	Plant ht (cm)	Duration (d)	Productive tillers (ns./plant)	Yield (g/plant)	Yield (t/ha)
DM24	122.7	105	15	25	4.6
DM25	125.7	106	15	24	4.6
DM28	131.3	105	12	22	4.2
DM38	121.7	105	14	23	4.1
Basmati 370	160.5	104	12	21	4.0
LSD (0.05)	4.2	ns	2	1	0.1

Table 2. Physicochemical characteristics of rice mutants and Basmati 370. Punjab, Pakistan.

Variety, mutant	Length ^a (mm)	Width ^a (mm)	Length-to-width ratio ^a	Quality index ^a	Elongation ratio ^a	Amylose ^b (%)
DM24	6.9	1.8	3.9	2.3	1.9	24
DM25	6.7	1.7	3.9	2.4	1.9	23
DM28	6.6	1.7	3.8	2.5	1.7	23
DM38	6.7	1.7	3.8	2.4	1.8	23
Basmati 370	6.9	1.8	3.8	2.3	1.8	23
LSD (0.05)	0.15	ns	ns	0.10	ns	ns

^aAv of 10 determinations. ^bAv of 3 determinations.

mutants were 18-24% shorter.

Yield samples were milled, polished, and evaluated for their physicochemical characteristics. All mutants had grain quality similar to Basmati 370 (Table 2). □

Upland rice varieties released in Burundi

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Upland rice has been planted for two centuries by Arabized populations along Lake Tanganyika. The Institut des Sciences Agronomiques du Burundi (ISABU) has decided to develop upland riziculture for 800-1300 m altitude in the Imbo and Kumoso plains.

In 1985, four improved varieties from IRAT and two local populations were evaluated at four stations (Fig. 1). Potential yields were estimated from yields in 30 15-cm pots. Statistical analysis of yields between varieties showed no significant difference at Bubanza ($F=2.13$), a highly significant difference at Mparambo ($F=5.58^{**}$), and a very highly significant difference at Moso ($F=10.47^{***}$) and Rumonge ($F=9.29^{***}$). Results are very highly significant for varieties ($F=19.6^{***}$),

1. Potential yield of 4 improved and 2 local varieties at 4 stations. Bujumbura, Burundi, 1985. Station altitude is in parentheses.

sites ($F=54.6^{***}$), and variety \times site interaction ($GXE-F=5.5^{***}$).

To isolate responsive varieties ($b > 1$) for intensive riziculture, a regression analysis of yield on environment was made (Fig. 2). Environment was taken to mean such diverse factors as fertility, water supply, climatology, and disease and is the mean of yields at each site.

Three varieties showed a positive interaction: IRAT104 ($b=1.47$), IRAT132 ($b=1.12$), IB45 ($b=1.17$). One, IB17, showed no interaction ($b=1$); and two, IRAT13 and IRAT101, were stable ($b < 1$). The stable nature of IRAT13 is attenuated by its susceptibility to *Sarocladium oryzae*, a major pest at middle altitudes (1000-1400 m) in Burundi.

IB45 showed total resistance to *S. oryzae*. All the IRAT varieties are susceptible. □

2. Regression analysis of yield.

Guarani, a high-yielding short-cycle upland rice for Midwest Brazil

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CNAx 095-BM30-BM9-28, a line selected from the cross IAC25/63-83 has been released as Guarani for Midwest Brazil.

Guarani is a short-duration variety (105-110 d), 100 cm tall. Leaves and spikelets are pubescent and panicles are semicompact, showing good spikelet fertility. Grains are 7.30 mm long and

2.67 mm wide with good cooking quality. In multilocation trials, it was superior to check in blast and drought resistance.

Overall average grain yield (2.7 t/ha) is 15% more than that of the traditionally grown short-duration IAC165 (see table). □

RY1 - a newly released upland variety for Zaire

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In 1976, seven varieties received from IRAT Cote d'Ivoire, were included in observational trials. RY1, RY2, and RY7 were selected for advanced yield trials 1977-80 in three locations, with R66 (check) and C4-1-5.

RY1 yields in Yangambi, Bambesa, and Boketa were 30% and 23% more than that of local check R66 (Table 1).

RY1 is moderately tall (142 cm), making hand harvesting easier and reducing lodging susceptibility in

Average grain yield of Guarani and IAC165 in 4 states of Brazil, 1982-86.

State	Trials (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)		Yield increase (%)
		Guarani	IAC165	
Goiás	41	2.8	2.5	14
Mato Grosso	12	2.6	2.2	17
Minas Gerais	7	2.4	1.9	26
Mato Grosso do Sul	7	2.2	2.1	6
Av		2.7	2.3	15